

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION ON LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND HOW IT CAN BE RAISED DURING THE CLASSES

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This study explains the impact of motivation in a foreign and second language acquisition. Motivation is a key factor in determining whether a student fails or succeeds while learning a language. In this paper, the researcher defines why motivation is so much crucial by defining the term itself - motivation at first, and gives instructions of how motivation can be raised in students through the help of the activities EFL/ESL teachers may use in the classroom.

Motivation is needed in any field to make something done. Motivation creates energy and energy enables a person to do any task more quickly and efficiently. Therefore it is one of the most essential tools in language learning as well. However, it is also considered a major issue in EFL/ESL acquisition which embarrasses both students and teachers most of the time. While students struggle with finding enough motivation, teachers struggle with getting students the source of that motivation. It is not only in Uzbekistan's case, but also in anywhere else in the world. As long as all teachers, students and even scientists agree with the idea that motivation plays the important role while acquiring a second or foreign language, we should find an answer to the question - how can we create motivation? Before addressing that question, what is motivation itself? What does it mean that someone is motivated?

"Motivation to learn a second language refers to the extent to which the individual works or tries to learn the language because of a desire to do so and the contentment experienced in this task" (Elizadeh, M. 2016). That is, motivation is a desire to learn the language, which provides one with the aim, intention to achieve that aim, and satisfaction of learning. Without their presence, one finds it very difficult to learn a language, even impossible. According to Narayan (2006), motivation is the reason behind one's action, which causes him to act toward his goal. It also affects the decisions we make while behaving toward a goal. There are many such definitions of motivation, all of which reassures that motivation is a key to learn a language. However, there must be something that generates the motivation. Williams and Burden (1997) state motivation is created by different influences, which can be either internal or external. In this manner motivation can be divided into two general types: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation (Deci E, Ryan RM. 1985). The intrinsic motivation is emerged when engaged in an activity that is enjoyable to do, while the extrinsic motivation are gained from external rewards for the activity done. For someone who is learning a language, it is very important both to enjoy the process of learning and to get rewards from surrounding such as being able to communicate in that very language, etc. in order to maintain learning. It means a language learner will need intrinsic and extrinsic motivation simultaneously. However, when compared in terms of their effectiveness, intrinsic motivation is considered more effective. According to Ushioda (2008) intrinsically motivated learners are more likely to display much higher levels of involvement in learning than the ones who are extrinsically motivated. When students engage in an activity because of their high curiosity to satisfy, they find that activity

intrinsically motivating, which will lead better learning. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is less beneficial in this manner. No matter which one is better, it is crucial to maintain motivation generally while learning a language. The same goes with learning English language too, as either EFL or ESL. Teachers play a major role to activate motivation in students, however, this is the part of teaching that teachers find most problematic. How can teachers tackle this problem? Here are some activities for rising motivation in ESL/EFL classrooms:

As it is widely known, the more interesting and exciting an activity is, the more engaged students are in the lesson, which gradually keeps students motivated and increases the odds that they will learn the language more effectively. One of such activities is Role playing. Role playing is an activity in which students work through a situation, event or a problem by performing certain roles (Sambisar, Naro W. 2018). In this activity, students can be either prepared for the their roles beforehand, by practicing or not prepared, generating their roles spontaneously, according to the teacher`s instructions. In both cases students find this activity exciting, because it gives them a chance to practice having conversation in different social contexts in different roles, making them imagine how it is like to be someone else and put it in a real world. Since they are performing someone else`s identity, they feel less shy to make mistakes. As a result, they get more confident as well. Eventually, students take actively part in learning process, even the passive ones. Teacher is more like a c while conducting role play activity. S/he observers how well students are doing in their roles and gives feedback at the end. In every social context that students are communicating on, there is a new language to be fed in and this is also what the teacher is responsible for. Teacher can feed in the new language to students during the time of acting or before it, during the rehearsal. Moreover, teachers are also allowed to participate themselves, in the role play, if necessary.

As mentioned earlier, how much exciting the activity is mostly determines how much motivated students will be. Kids love to compete, teens and adults are not exception either. No matter what they are competing on, such as sports, games, etc. they always try to do their best due to the intense desire to win. If competition causes students to do their very best and leads to incredible results, why not to introduce competition into ESL/EFL classroom too, in order to improve learning process? Students may get competitive with each other for better grades in quizzes and tests that the teacher conducts. Trying to get the teacher`s recognition can also force them to compete. However, games are the easiest way to get students competing. For example:

Divide the students into two teams and cross the board for the very two teams. Then tell them to go to the board one by one from each team and write as many words as they can, related to a particular topic and in certain period of time. Make sure that they do not duplicate from one another, while standing on the board next to each other and at the end, announce the team as the winner who has written more correct words.

Tell the students whoever finishes the writing exercise (it could be any exercise from any aspect e.g. grammar, vocabulary, reading exercises) first, will get a chance to select a song to listen to in the classroom or gets some other type of reward. However, make sure the reward that you choose is appealing and attractive to students.

There are a great amount of games that are competitive and teachers can also create them on their own, using their imagination. Except being motivational, competitive games also improve students` independent skills and prepare them for the real-world challenge of

competition, which makes them one of the most necessary activities that must be held in ESL/EFL classrooms.

Whenever a teacher puts students into group work, collaboration is part of the process. Students collaborate as separate teams and help their teammates in order to have the task done. Higher level students can help lower level students with their confusing points and correct their language-related mistakes, as well. Students can explain something in a way students can understand more easily than they do from a teacher's explanation. Therefore, students always find it both more helpful and comfortable to learn from their peers. And this increases their knowledge significantly, which will boost their confidence and motivation as a result.

Having students in groups always gets them practicing speaking more. In ESL/EFL classrooms, nothing is more intimidating than speaking among other skills. Intimidation can be minimized through the help of group work where students speak more by having discussions or debates. The more they speak, the faster it becomes a natural part of their identity to speak in the language they are learning. Consequently, it eliminates the intimidation and makes the students better speakers gradually. And performing better in their speeches keeps them always motivated.

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